

Electronegativity and Hardness : A Density Functional Treatment†

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Representing a multitude of apparently disjoint phenomena in terms of a few parameters has been a widely-shared goal for all scientists. Two such key parameters in the chemical literature are electronegativity and hardness. Pauling¹ was the first person to introduce the concept of electronegativity in chemistry. His definition of electronegativity, viz. 'the power of an atom in a molecule to attract electrons to itself', has been proved useful in correlating various fields of chemical knowledge and experience². Not many chemists paid attention to the concept of electronegativity because of its empirical nature as is discernible from several definitions³⁻²⁹ of electronegativity until very recently Parr *et al.*²¹ provided with a rigorous theoretical definition, within the density functional theory, through its correlation with chemical potential. A quantum-thermodynamic definition had also been proposed earlier by Gyftopoulos and Hatsopoulos¹⁵.

Among various electronegativity scales, Pauling¹ and Mulliken³ scales have been popular for a very wide cross-section of chemists. It is apparent from Pauling's definition of electronegativity that it is not the property of the isolated atom but it depends on the molecular environment in which the atom is in. Pauling had given his relative electronegativity scale based on the thermochemical data. He argued that any heteronuclear species would be more stable than their homonuclear counterparts owing to the fact that the corresponding electronegativity difference would stabilise the molecule by ionic-covalent resonance energy. Unlike Pauling scale, Mulliken scale is the absolute one because it depends on fundamental energy values for isolated atoms. Mulliken defined the electronegativity as the average of the ionisation potential and the electron affinity of the isolated atom. This definition is important because it has bearing in the modern density functional definition²¹ of electronegativity. Other methods consider electronegativity to be some function, e.g. energy, force, etc., of size and charge. Allred and Rochow⁵ electronegativity is defined as the electrostatic force exerted by the valence electrons while Sanderson¹² defined it in terms of relative electron density.

A promising new scale has been suggested by Allen²⁵ who considers the electronegativity to be the third dimension (energy) in the periodic table,

the other two being the atomic number and the number of shells respectively. In this spectroscopic scale, the electronegativity is defined as average one-electron energy of the valence-shell electrons for the isolated atoms in their ground states. These values match very well with Pauling¹ and Allred-Rochow^{5,6} values and have provided chemically meaningful bond polarity values³⁰ between atoms in a molecule. Considering these aspects this scale is considered^{25,30} to be 'the first quantitative quantum mechanical realisation of Pauling electronegativity scale'.

So far we have been considering the electronegativity of atoms either in the free state or in a molecular environment. The electronegativity of the molecule from the constituent atoms is generally obtained by taking the geometric mean. The genesis of this calculation is based on Sanderson's principle³¹ which states that when a molecule is formed from atoms the electronegativities get equalised and the final value of the molecular electronegativity is given by the geometric average of the electronegativities of the individual atoms³². Sanderson's principle has been endorsed by other workers^{33,34} and has also been modified to include external potential effects³⁵. The importance of electrostatic interaction between atoms and their influence on atoms in a molecule has also been studied by others³⁶⁻³⁸. An important outcome of these studies is the idea of electronegativity equalisation in terms of the harmonic mean³⁵ of the valence state atom's electronegativities in a molecule.

In studying a variety of acid-base chemical reactions, Pearson³⁹⁻⁴⁴ understood the necessity of a second parameter apart from the electronegativity. He³⁹ introduced the concepts of hardness and softness for this purpose and categorised different acids and bases based on their properties as follows. (i) Acids, the acceptors of electrons, are termed as hard if they do not have easily-excited outer electrons and have small sizes and high positive charges; otherwise they are soft acids. (ii) Bases, the donors of electrons, are called hard if they have low polarizabilities, high electronegativity values, are hard to oxidise and associated with empty orbitals of high energy; other bases are soft.

The importance of this nomenclature is in the hard and soft acids and bases principle, popularly known as HSAB principle³⁹. It states that 'Hard

† Dedicated to Professor S. C. Rakshit on the occasion of 65th birth anniversary.

acids prefer to react with hard bases and soft acids prefer to react with soft bases'. This principle is based on both thermodynamic and kinetic stability and accordingly helped classifying a wide variety of chemical facts.

In this review article we try to present the physical basis of concepts like chemical hardness and electronegativity within density functional theory. Section 1 provides an introduction to density functional theory while the concept of chemical potential is enunciated in Section 2. Sections 3 and 4 describe global and local hardness properties respectively. Finally, Section 5 contains some concluding remarks.

Density functional theory : An overview

Formulation of the many particle problem in the single-particle framework demands the replacement of the many-particle wave-function by a suitable quantity of atmost three variables. Single-particle density $\rho(\vec{r})$ is a candidate^{4,5} for the same and for a normalised $|\psi\rangle$ of an N -electron system it is defined as

$$\rho(\vec{r}) = N \int \psi^*(\vec{x}_1, \vec{x}_2, \dots, \vec{x}_N) \psi(\vec{x}_1, \vec{x}_2, \dots, \vec{x}_N) d\vec{r}_2 \dots d\vec{r}_N \quad (1.1)$$

where \vec{x}_i stands for both space and spin coordinates for i -th electron. Density functional theory^{4,6-48} attempts to use $\rho(\vec{r})$ as the fundamental variable of an electronic structure theory for different many-electron systems encompassing atoms, molecules and solids. The single-particle density $\rho(\vec{r})$ may get the status similar to that of the many-particle wave-function $\psi(\vec{x}_1, \vec{x}_2, \dots, \vec{x}_N)$ only if the former contains almost all the informations obtainable from the latter. At least for the ground state or the lowest state of a given symmetry, this has been proved to be true by Hohenberg and Kohn^{4,8} in terms of their following important theorems.

(i) The nondegenerate ground state of an N -electron system moving under the influence of their mutual coulomb repulsion and a static external single-particle potential $v(\vec{r})$, arising, say, from a set of nuclei is completely characterised by $\rho(\vec{r})$, i.e. $v(\vec{r})$, ψ and hence all ground-state properties of the system are unique functionals of the density. For studying time-dependent situations^{50,51} and excited states^{52,53}, one needs to know the current density $\vec{j}(\vec{r}, t)$ which is obtainable from the continuity equation,

$$\frac{\partial \rho(\vec{r}, t)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \vec{j}(\vec{r}, t) = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

(ii) For a given external potential, the energy functional assumes a minimum value for the true

density. Therefore, the variational minimisation of the energy functional $E[\rho]$ (first theorem allows one to write E in terms of ρ alone) with respect to the trial density, conserving the total number of particles, may be regarded as an alternative to the usual Rayleigh-Ritz variational scheme in wavefunction-based quantum mechanics. In other words, the ground state density (and hence all other quantities including the energy) is obtainable through minimisation of $E[\rho]$ with respect to ρ subject to the following normalisation condition,

$$\int \rho(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} = N \quad (1.3)$$

as a constraint, i.e. using the stationary condition,

$$\delta \{E[\rho] - \mu \int \rho(\vec{r}) d\vec{r}\} = 0 \quad (1.4)$$

or equivalently, in terms of the familiar Euler-Lagrange equation,

$$\frac{\delta E[\rho]}{\delta \rho} - \mu = 0 \quad (1.5)$$

where μ is a Lagrange multiplier and has been interpreted as chemical potential²¹ or the electronegativity which measures the escaping tendency of an electron cloud. Therefore, density functional theory is an electronic structure theory of ground (equilibrium) electronic states in which the electronegativity of chemistry plays the similar role in density-based variational principle as being played by energy in usual variational scheme in wavefunction based quantum mechanics. This clearly indicates that the density functional theory can describe the chemistry well.

Problem comes in implementing the variational technique, starting from the Euler equation (1.5), because the Hohenberg-Kohn theorem being merely an existence theorem suggests nothing regarding the functional form for $E[\rho]$ and its exact form is still unknown. In order to have a good approximate form for $E[\rho]$ one tries to decompose it and to characterise the components whose forms are known. Writing $E[\rho]$ as⁵⁴

$$E[\rho] = F[\rho] + \int v(\vec{r}) \rho(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} \quad (1.6)$$

where $F[\rho]$ is a universal functional comprising kinetic and electron-electron interaction energies and, thus, can again be decomposed as

$$F[\rho] = G[\rho] + \frac{1}{2} \iint \frac{\rho(\vec{r}) \rho(\vec{r}')}{|\vec{r} - \vec{r}'|} d\vec{r} d\vec{r}' \quad (1.7)$$

In equation (1.7) the functional $G[\rho]$ consists of kinetic and exchange-correlation energy functionals. Therefore, the total energy functional can be written as

$$E[\rho] = \int v(\vec{r}) \rho(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} + \frac{1}{2} \iint \frac{\rho(\vec{r}) \rho(\vec{r}')}{|\vec{r} - \vec{r}'|} d\vec{r} d\vec{r}' + T[\rho] + E_{xc}[\rho] \quad (1.8)$$

Exact forms for $T[\rho]$ and $E_{xc}[\rho]$ are not known. Since $T[\rho]$ dominates over $E_{xc}[\rho]$, both locally and

globally, the construction of proper kinetic energy functional with acceptable local and global behaviours as well as the correct functional derivative has been considered^{5,6} to be the crux of the problems in density functional theory. Various approximations to the kinetic energy functional^{5,6} and the exchange-correlation energy functional and their subsequent refinements provide better forms for $E[\rho]$ and hence better densities from the solution of the Euler equation (1.5).

There is another approach where in the spirit of Hartree theory, one considers^{5,4} a system of N non-interacting fermions moving under a static effective self-consistent one-body potential $v_{\text{eff}}(\vec{r})$ and accordingly the Euler-Lagrange equation becomes

$$\frac{\delta T[\rho]}{\delta \rho} + v_{\text{eff}}(\vec{r}) = \mu \quad (1.9)$$

where,

$$v_{\text{eff}}(\vec{r}) = v(\vec{r}) + \int \frac{\rho(\vec{r}')}{|\vec{r} - \vec{r}'|} d\vec{r}' + \frac{\delta E_{xc}[\rho]}{\delta \rho} \quad (1.10)$$

Equation (1.9) transforms into a set of one-particle Hartree-like equations,

$$[-\frac{1}{2}\nabla^2 + v_{\text{eff}}(\vec{r})]\phi_i = \epsilon_i \phi_i \quad (1.11)$$

and the electron density is obtained as the following sum over the lowest N normalised solutions,

$$\rho(\vec{r}) = \sum_i^{N_{\text{occ}}} \rho_i(\vec{r}) = \sum_i^{N_{\text{occ}}} |\phi_i|^2 \quad (1.12)$$

In this picture the kinetic and total energies are given by

$$T = \sum_i \epsilon_i - \int \rho(\vec{r}) v_{\text{eff}}(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} \quad (1.13)$$

and

$$E = \sum_i \epsilon_i - \frac{1}{2} \iint \frac{\rho(\vec{r})\rho(\vec{r}')}{|\vec{r} - \vec{r}'|} d\vec{r}d\vec{r}' + E_{xc}[\rho] - \int \rho(\vec{r}) \frac{\delta E_{xc}[\rho]}{\delta \rho} d\vec{r} \quad (1.14)$$

The Lagrange multiplier μ associated with the normalisation constraint in density functional theory (DFT) has been considered to have important chemical significance and has been characterised as the chemical potential of the electron cloud and is constant throughout the system. Its connection²¹ with the electronegativity χ helps evaluating the latter from a quantum mechanical definition and also provides the theoretical justification for the principle of electronegativity equalisation^{3,1} during molecule formation. Density functional definition of electronegativity is based on the analogous definition given by Mulliken³ as follows,

$$\chi = \frac{I+A}{2} \quad (1.15)$$

where I and A are the ionisation potential and the electron affinity of the system concerned respectively. The genesis of this definition is in the answer of the question, 'Given two species A and B , which is more electronegative?' If there is an electron transfer from B to A the energy requirement for A is $(I_B - A_A)$, while B would require the energy $(I_A - A_B)$ if it accepts an electron from A . Electronegativities would be equal if these two requirements are the same, viz.

$$I_B - A_A = I_A - A_B ; I_A + A_A = I_B + A_B \quad (1.16)$$

and the value is as given in formula (1.15) within an arbitrary scale factor of 1/2. Now the right-hand-side of equation (1.15) is nothing but a three-point finite difference approximation to $(-\partial E/\partial N)$ because

$$\begin{aligned} \chi &= \frac{I+A}{2} = \frac{(E_{N-1} - E_N) + (E_N - E_{N+1})}{2} \\ &= -\frac{E_{N+1} - E_{N-1}}{2(\Delta N)} \simeq -\left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial N}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (1.17)$$

Equation (1.17) and the Euler equation (1.5) together provides the density functional correlation between χ and μ as

$$\begin{aligned} \chi &= -\left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial N}\right) = -\int d\vec{r} (\delta E/\delta \rho)(\delta \rho/\delta N) \\ &= -\mu \int (\delta \rho/\delta N) d\vec{r} = -\mu \end{aligned} \quad (1.18)$$

Although this definition of electronegativity is quite straightforward it has been criticised²⁷ for creating unnecessary confusion. However, the confusion and misunderstanding can be avoided²⁶ if one can keep track of which electronegativity measure one is talking about.

The importance of the change in chemical potential of a species with addition or removal of electrons has been highlighted by Parr and Pearson^{5,6}. They have identified^{5,6} this property with the absolute chemical hardness η associated with the HSAB principle of Pearson^{3,9} as

$$\eta = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial N}\right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial N^2}\right) \simeq \frac{I-A}{2} \quad (1.19)$$

Thus DFT provides important workable quantitative definitions for the hitherto qualitative popular chemical properties like electronegativity (chemical potential) and chemical hardness.

Chemical potential : The first derivative

The formal similarity between the Lagrange multiplier (μ) in the Euler equation of DFT and the chemical potential of an open system is the origin of identifying μ as the chemical potential²¹ and $\chi = -\mu$ as the electronegativity^{15,21} as shown in equation (1.18). We have seen in Section 1 how

chemical potential for an isolated system (or equivalently in the microcanonical ensemble of statistical mechanics) is defined. For the ground state of such systems, the energy $E[\rho]$ reaches its minimum among densities ρ that integrates to the total number of electrons N . Similarly, for an equilibrium state at temperature θ of a closed system (canonical ensemble), the Helmholtz free energy $A[\rho]$ goes to the minimum among densities normalised to N . For an open system (grand canonical ensemble) the equilibrium state at a particular temperature θ and chemical potential μ is characterised by the minimum value of the grand potential $\Omega[\rho]$ among all ρ . At the zero-temperature limit, the equilibrium states defined in last two cases would be identical to the corresponding ground states. It ought to be emphasised that usual Hilbert space treatment is not valid for the grand canonical ensemble study since the number of particles in any member of the ensemble is not conserved. Extending the constrained search formulation⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹ of DFT in Fock space Perdew *et al.*²² defined a universal variational functional for treating open systems as

$$F_{\text{open}}[\rho(\vec{r})] = \text{Min}_{\Gamma \rightarrow \rho} \text{Tr} [\hat{\Gamma}(\hat{T} + \hat{V}_{ee})] \quad (2.1)$$

where $\hat{\Gamma}$, \hat{T} and \hat{V}_{ee} are density, kinetic energy and electron-electron repulsion energy operators respectively. Therefore, the grand potential at the zero-temperature limit becomes,

$$\Omega[\rho] = F_{\text{open}}[\rho] + \int \rho(\vec{r})(v(\vec{r}) - \mu) d\vec{r} \quad (2.2)$$

The convexity of the energy for atoms and molecules allows⁴⁷ one to extend the grand canonical ensemble theory to its zero-temperature limit and accordingly the definition of the chemical potential becomes the following key equation in finite temperature DFT,

$$\frac{\delta F_{\text{open}}[\rho]}{\delta \rho(\vec{r})} + v(\vec{r}) = \mu \quad (2.3)$$

Equivalently, one can write μ as

$$\begin{aligned} \mu &= \text{Lt}_{\theta \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial N} \right)_{\theta, v(\vec{r})} = \text{Lt}_{\theta \rightarrow 0} \left[\left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial N} \right)_{\theta, v(\vec{r})} - \theta \left(\frac{\partial S}{\partial N} \right)_{\theta, v(\vec{r})} \right] \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

For a three-state model of an \bar{N} -electron species, along with its positive and negative ions, in a zero temperature grand canonical ensemble μ has been shown^{15,22,47} to be

$$\mu_{\theta=0} = \begin{cases} -I & \bar{N}-1 < N < \bar{N} \\ -\frac{I+A}{2} & N = \bar{N} \\ -A & \bar{N}+1 > N > \bar{N} \end{cases} \quad (2.5)$$

and the energy in this limit is a continuous series of straight-line segments.

Chemical potential μ may appear in pure ground state theory if the latter is assumed to be an extension of the corresponding grand canonical theory⁴⁷. However, the concept of μ comes in canonical ensemble theory rather straightforwardly in terms of the following finite-difference formulae⁵⁷,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu^- &= \frac{E(N-1) - E(N)}{-1} = -I \text{ (Removal of electron)} \\ \mu^+ &= E(N+1) - E(N) = -A \text{ (Addition of electron)} \\ \mu^0 &= -\frac{I+A}{2} \text{ (Neutral species)} \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

Excited state information may be incorporated in chemical potential if one resorts to other ensembles like one appears in 'apparatus' density functional theory proposed by Tachibana⁵⁸. It is worth noting that although we use the Euler equation (1.5) as the definition for μ in most of the ground state calculations it is different from its correct definition $\left(\frac{\delta E}{\delta \rho} \right)_{N, v(\vec{r})}$. The difference has been shown to be a constant⁵⁹, viz.,

$$\left(\frac{\delta E}{\delta \rho} \right)_{N, v(\vec{r})} - \left(\frac{\delta E}{\delta \rho} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} = \text{constant} \quad (2.7)$$

which is, however, not calculable with the available information.

The calculation of μ is generally accomplished within X_α theory with and without spin polarization⁶⁰⁻⁶² or the self-interaction-corrected version of it⁶³. In these theories μ is identified to the highest occupied orbital energy. It ought to be emphasised²⁶ that the chemical potential (electronegativity) being discussed here is altogether different from the original electronegativity idea of Pauling¹. While Pauling's definition presupposes the concept of atom-in-a-molecule, the density functional counterpart of it is applicable to the overall species may it be an atom or a molecule or a radical or an ion and accordingly the latter quantities are called absolute electronegativities⁶⁶. The absolute values are useful in understanding the chemical reactivity of a system and have been found^{64,65} to provide an estimate of the initial interaction between two such systems. Pauling scale, on the other hand, is known to be very good in estimating bond polarities and the strength of the bonds between different atoms. Considering the validity of the atoms-in-a-molecule concept, without going into the relative merits and demerits of different definitions depending on different partitioning schemes^{21,66-69}, one may still get valuable molecular information from the old formulae, may be after proper modifications⁷⁰, using atomic absolute electronegativity values in stead of the Pauling values.

A qualitative guideline regarding the age-old query of chemists, viz. 'What do atoms do when they unite to form a molecule?', is being provided by Sanderson's principle^{1,2,31} which states that the electronegativities of atoms get equalised during molecule formulation. Density functional theory provides^{21,71} rigorous justification for Sanderson's Principle as well as for³² the related geometric mean postulate^{72,73}: the molecular electronegativity (chemical potential) is given by the geometric mean of the original atomic electronegativities (chemical potentials). The chemical potential equalisation principle draws analogy from the similar concept in classical macroscopic thermodynamics. During the formation of a diatomic molecule PQ, from its constituent atoms P and Q, there will be a flow of electrons from Q to P if $\mu_Q^0 > \mu_P^0$ where the last two quantities are the original atomic chemical potentials. Using the definitions for μ and η , equations (1.18) and (1.19), and ignoring all other effects, we have the following Taylor series expansion of the energy values for a small amount of charge transfer,

$$\begin{aligned} E_P &= E_P^0 + \mu_P^0 (N_P - N_P^0) + \eta_P (N_P - N_P^0)^2 + \dots \\ E_Q &= E_Q^0 + \mu_Q^0 (N_Q - N_Q^0) + \eta_Q (N_Q - N_Q^0)^2 + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

and accordingly, the total energy is given by

$$E_P + E_Q = E_P^0 + E_Q^0 + (\mu_P^0 - \mu_Q^0) \Delta N + (\eta_P + \eta_Q) (\Delta N)^2 + \dots \quad (2.9)$$

where

$$\Delta N = N_Q^0 - N_Q = N_P - N_P^0 \quad (2.10)$$

Therefore, the system will be stabilised, at least for small ΔN , if electrons flow from Q to P in case $\mu_Q^0 > \mu_P^0$. While the stabilisation energy is second order in $\Delta \mu^0 (= \mu_Q^0 - \mu_P^0)$, the charge transfer (ΔN) to first order is proportional to $\Delta \mu^0$. The latter aspect has been known intuitively for ages¹ through the empirical relations connecting the dipole moment and the electronegativity difference. Minimising $E_P + E_Q$ (equation 2.9) with respect to ΔN , we get Sanderson's principle, viz.

$$\mu_P = \mu_Q \quad (2.11)$$

where
$$\mu_P = \left(\frac{\partial E_P}{\partial N_P} \right)_v = \mu_P^0 + 2\eta_P \Delta N + \dots \quad (2.12)$$

and
$$\mu_Q = \left(\frac{\partial E_Q}{\partial N_Q} \right)_v = \mu_Q^0 + 2\eta_Q \Delta N + \dots$$

It may be noted that geometric mean principle suggests

$$\mu_P = \mu_Q = (\mu_P^0 \mu_Q^0)^{1/2} \quad (2.13)$$

In what follows,

$$\Delta N = \frac{\Delta \mu^0}{2(\eta_P + \eta_Q)} \quad (2.14)$$

and

$$\Delta E = - \frac{(\Delta \mu^0)^2}{4(\eta_P + \eta_Q)}$$

The dependence of the above quantities on hardness values would be taken care of in the subsequent sections. There have been several modifications of the old naive formulae discussed above. However, the basic idea remains the same. Full second order expansion of the energy in an atoms-in-a-molecule framework^{74,75} has helped³⁸ explaining HSAB principle⁶⁶ in terms of electronegativity equalisation. It has been argued⁷⁶ that Sanderson's principle would exhibit increasing deviations with increasing hardness values for constituent atoms.

The calculation of atomic charges in molecule⁷⁷ (population analysis) has been known to be important in understanding various chemical effects⁷⁸. The electronegativity equalisation concept offers a simple and interesting⁷⁹⁻⁸¹ technique for population analysis. This procedure yields very good partial charges for a molecule as large as alanine dipeptide⁷⁹ when compared with the corresponding STO-3G values.

Before we leave this section, we will mention some interesting density functional aspects of electronegativity in understanding electronic structure theory. The electrostatic potential $\phi(r)$ calculated at the covalent radius of an atom has been considered¹⁶ to be an alternative definition for electronegativity. Incorporating this concept into DFT (especially the Euler equation 1.5) Politzer *et al.* obtained atomic radii^{82,83} and Wigner-Seitz radii⁸⁴ for several systems. This definition can be used as a constraint⁸⁵ to have a new self-consistent field scheme for atomic electronic structure calculations. Diamagnetic shielding constant values have been shown⁸⁶ to decrease with an increase in electronegativity by loss of electrons. For very large atomic number (Z) limit of neutral atoms the electronegativity goes as⁸⁷ $Z^{-1/3}$, a reminiscent of Thomas-Fermi type theories⁸⁸. Constancy of μ in space has been used⁸⁹ as a constraint in improving energies from approximate wave functions. A formula like (2.14) helps⁹⁰ relating Pauling and Mulliken electronegativity values. A promising semiempirical DFT of chemical binding has been explored⁹¹ in terms of two new ideas, viz. the bond electronegativity and the bond hardness. Electronegativity difference and hardness sum have been used successfully⁹² as coordinates in the structure-stability diagrams.

Chemical hardness : The second derivative

Considering the importance of concepts like hardness and softness⁴⁴ in understanding a variety of chemical reactions, Parr and Pearson⁵⁶ provided the following definition of hardness in terms of the compressibility of the electron fluid,

$$\eta = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial N} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial N^2} \right) \sim \frac{I - A}{2} \quad (1.19)$$

Softness S is considered⁹³ to be the reciprocal of η ,

$$S = \frac{2}{I - A} \quad (3.1)$$

A grand canonical ensemble description⁴⁷ at absolute zero temperature provides the curvature of the energy as a function of the number of electrons as

$$2\eta = \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial N^2} \right)_{\theta \rightarrow 0} = \text{Lt}_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} \left[\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} (\partial E / \partial N)_{\beta}}{(\partial N / \partial \mu)_{\beta}} \right] \quad (3.2)$$

which reduces to

$$2\eta = \begin{cases} 0 & , N < \bar{N} \\ \text{Lt}_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} [\eta_0 e^{\beta \eta_0}] = \infty & , N = \bar{N} \\ 0 & , N > \bar{N} \end{cases} \quad (3.3)$$

where $\eta_0 = (I - A)/2$ is the absolute chemical hardness defined above.

The usual finite difference formula appears automatically in the canonical ensemble picture as

$$\eta = \frac{1}{2} [E(N+1) - E(N) - \{E(N) - E(N-1)\}] = \frac{1}{2} (I - A) \quad (3.4)$$

In the molecular orbital theory η is half of the HOMO-LUMO energy difference whereas for a semiconductor or an insulator it is the half of the band gap. In order to understand the physical meaning of hardness one generally resorts to the following disproportionation reaction where an electron goes from A to A , viz.

and the associated energy given by

$$\Delta E = I_A - A_A \quad (3.6)$$

is twice the hardness.

The above disproportionation reaction (3.5) has been a recurring theme in the orbital theories of electronic structure for about last six decades. In Hückel-type theories ΔE is zero and may be rationalised considering the energies for two electrons in \ddot{A}^- and for one electron in each of the two \dot{A} are same. A better estimate for ΔE would be the repulsion between the two valence electrons in \ddot{A}^- . The interesting idea of using equation (3.6) or equivalently the hardness for calculating the electron repulsion term originated in the works of Moffitt⁶⁹ and Pariser⁹⁴. These ideas were later improved to give PPP, CNDO, MINDO type electronic structure theories⁹⁴ and the so-called Hubbard model in solid state physics. Further refinements lead to a semiempirical density functional theory⁹¹.

Hardness and softness concepts appear in various diverse fields. Hardness-softness concept⁹⁵ is intimately connected with the statistical interpretation of bond index, valence and charge fluctuations⁹³. The softness has been shown to be analogous to the capacity of a spherical condenser and the obvious extension

is the proportionality between softness and the inter-nuclear distance in a molecule^{34,70,96,97} as becomes apparent within a bond-charge model^{91,98-100}. The latter idea may be extended to get hardness values for a neutral species through the application of a finite difference formula¹⁰¹ and making use of the chemical potentials for the corresponding positive and negative ions obtainable as the respective electrostatic potentials at covalent radii⁹² (see also Komorowski⁹⁶). Hardness is found¹⁰² to be linear in frequency of vertical transition associated with λ_{max} for several molecules. The thermodynamic relationship between compressibility and chemical hardness helps understanding and provides a measure for the macroscopic mechanical hardness for a mineral¹⁰³. Important insights into different chemical problems¹⁰⁴ can be obtained from the chemical hardness. It is a good measure of aromaticity¹⁰⁵ of organic compounds. Aromatic and antiaromatic substances can be differentiated easily in terms of a new index called relative hardness¹⁰⁶ while the activation hardness is introduced¹⁰⁷ to study the orientation of electrophilic aromatic substitution. A very small η value may characterise a super-conducting state¹⁰⁸ since equation (2.14) predicts a very large flow of electrons.

An alternate way of defining softness is through the analogous macroscopic thermodynamic quantity given by the following⁹³ fluctuation formula in a grand canonical ensemble,

$$S = \left(\frac{\partial \langle N \rangle}{\partial \mu} \right)_{V,T} = \frac{1}{kT} [\langle (N^2) \rangle - \langle (N) \rangle^2] \quad (3.7)$$

Different ensembles provide different fluctuation formulas¹⁰⁹ and some of them may be useful in understanding chemisorption and catalysis⁹³.

Now, there arises an obvious question, 'what happens to the hardness or softness parameter when atoms form molecule?' or more precisely, 'is there any companion principle to the geometric mean principle from electronegativity equalisation (discussed in the previous section)?'. It has been shown¹¹⁰ that softness of a molecule is, to a reasonable approximation, given by the arithmetic mean of the softness of the constituent atoms while a geometric mean of atomic hardness values provides^{111,112} the estimate for the molecular hardness. An important consequence may be the hardness equalisation principle^{109,111}. This may provide the direction of a chemical reaction, much like the second law of thermodynamics, through a principle of a maximum hardness^{113,114,105-107} which states¹¹³ - 'There seems to be a rule of nature that molecules arrange themselves so as to be as hard as possible'. This principle provides¹¹⁵ a formal proof for the HSAB principle when coupled with the original Parr-Pearson idea⁵⁶. Equation (2.14) or various refinements thereof^{98,79,116} form the quantitative representation of the HSAB principle. Predominantly covalent bonding occurs when $(\eta_D + \eta_O)$ is small implying more energy lowering

and a large flow of electrons. However, the ionic bonding initiated by the electrostatic (coulomb) interaction between charges and dipoles takes over in the large η case. It should be emphasised that the Klopman theory of chemical reactivity^{117,118} in terms of two different types of chemical reactions, viz. charge-controlled and frontier-controlled, may have a bearing in two types of interactions, viz. hard-hard (h-h) and soft-soft (s-s), discussed here. The frontier-controlled reactions are explained within the frontier-orbital theory¹¹⁹⁻¹²¹ according to which the HOMO and the LUMO or a few more orbitals in their neighborhood are sufficient to explain and contain all information about these reactions. However, the description of these reactions within DFT requires the local quantities whose introduction is deferred to the next section. The s-s interactions are mainly stabilised by covalent bonding³⁸ originated from the transfer of electrons while the ionic bonding provides the stability of the h-h interactions through change in external potential. It may be noted that the positivity of atomic hardness values automatically assures^{122,123} the internal stability. The hard-soft interactions may alternatively be described¹²⁴ in terms of the compressibility and the 'lumpiness' of the electron density measured through its Laplacian. Large extrema of $\nabla^2\rho$ refer to the hard sites in a molecule.

Local quantities

The theory of chemical reactivity ought to be local because any such theory requires a detailed knowledge of site selectivity in a chemical species may it be atom, molecule or solid. Accordingly, the global quantities discussed so far will be inadequate in understanding reactivity and would force one to resort to their local counterparts. In order to better appreciate the nature of these local quantities, a change from one ground state to another is considered. The changes in energy and in chemical potential associated with the above change or for an equilibrium state in the grand canonical ensemble at 0 K would, within DFT, be given by⁴⁷

$$dE = \mu dN + \int \rho(\vec{r}) dv(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} \quad (4.1)$$

$$\text{and } d\mu = 2\eta dN + \int f(\vec{r}) dv(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} \quad (4.2)$$

where the quantity $f(\vec{r})$ is called¹²⁵ the frontier function or the Fukui function and is defined as

$$f(\vec{r}) \equiv (\partial\rho(\vec{r})/\partial N)_v = (\delta\mu/\delta v(\vec{r}))_N \quad (4.3)$$

by a Maxwell relation¹²⁶ of equation (5.1). Fukui function is a local quantity and has been found¹²⁵ to be the key concept in the density functional approach to the frontier electron theory of chemical reactivity. There are three types of Fukui function to characterise the stereoselectivity of different species and are defined as

$$f^+(\vec{r}) = \rho_{N+1}(\vec{r}) - \rho_N(\vec{r}) \quad (\text{for nucleophilic attack}) \quad (4.4a)$$

$$f^-(\vec{r}) = \rho_N(\vec{r}) - \rho_{N-1}(\vec{r}) \quad (\text{for electrophilic attack}) \quad (4.4b)$$

$$f^0(\vec{r}) = [\rho_{N+1}(\vec{r}) - \rho_{N-1}(\vec{r})]/2 \quad (\text{for radical attack}) \quad (4.4c)$$

where ρ_{N+1} , ρ_N and ρ_{N-1} are the electron densities for the negative, neutral and positive molecules respectively, all of which are considered to be of the same geometric structure. Within the 'frozen core' approximation, f^+ is the LUMO orbital density and f^- is the HOMO orbital density. This makes the connection between the frontier orbital theory¹¹⁹⁻¹²¹ and the density functional theory justifying the name Fukui function (frontier function)¹²⁵ given to $f(\vec{r})$. It has been demonstrated¹²⁷ that $f(\vec{r})$, indeed, is able to demonstrate the chemical reactivity in CO, CN⁻ and HCHO molecules. It is worth-mentioning that three different Fukui functions arise naturally because of the discontinuity²² in the derivative given in equation (4.3) and three possible, viz. forward, backward and central finite difference approximations to this derivative.

Similarly, these finite difference approximations from Mulliken population analysis in atoms and molecules give rise to condensed Fukui functions¹²⁸ as follows,

$$f_j^+ = q_j(N+1) - q_j(N) \quad (\text{for nucleophilic attack}) \quad (4.5a)$$

$$f_j^- = q_j(N) - q_j(N-1) \quad (\text{for electrophilic attack}) \quad (4.5b)$$

$$f_j^0 = [q_j(N+1) - q_j(N-1)]/2 \quad (\text{for radical attack}) \quad (4.5c)$$

where q_j is the gross charge of atom j in a molecule. Gas phase basicity for different amines have been successfully analysed¹²⁸ through the use of condensed Fukui functions. The work of Yang *et al.*¹²⁹ may also be seen for explicit formulas for $f^\pm(\vec{r})$ in terms of frontier orbital densities within the Kohn-Sham Scheme.

The space dependent variant of the softness S is the local softness $s(\vec{r})$ defined as

$$s(\vec{r}) = S f(\vec{r}) = \left[\frac{\partial\rho(\vec{r})}{\partial\mu} \right]_{v(\vec{r})} \quad (4.6)$$

such that

$$S = \int s(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} \quad (4.7)$$

Therefore, $s(\vec{r})$ contains all information about relative site reactivity in a molecule as obtainable from the Fukui function as a normalised local softness.

It may be noted that knowing $s(\vec{r})$ means knowing $f(\vec{r})$ but reverse is not true¹⁰⁹. A consequence of equality (4.3) is an alternative definition¹⁰⁹ for $s(\vec{r})$, viz.

$$s(\vec{r}) = - \left(\frac{\delta N}{\delta v(\vec{r})} \right) \quad (4.8)$$

Within a grand ensemble framework a fluctuation formula for defining $s(\vec{r})$ can be as follows⁹³,

$$s(\vec{r}) = \frac{1}{kT} [\langle \rho(\vec{r})N \rangle - \langle N \rangle \langle \rho(\vec{r}) \rangle] \quad (4.9)$$

A natural definition for the local hardness $\eta(\vec{r})$ would be^{130,131}

$$\eta(\vec{r}) = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\delta \mu}{\delta \rho(\vec{r})} \right]_{v(\vec{r})} \quad (4.10)$$

Substituting μ from the Euler equation (1.5) we have^{130,131}

$$\eta(\vec{r}) = \frac{1}{2N} \int \frac{\delta^2 F[\rho]}{\delta \rho(\vec{r}) \delta \rho(\vec{r}')} \rho(\vec{r}') d\vec{r}' \quad (4.11)$$

where $F[\rho]$ is the universal functional discussed in Section 1. It can be shown¹³⁰ that unlike local softness, a simple integration of $\eta(\vec{r})$ over all space does not give the global hardness η , rather

$$\eta = \int f(\vec{r}) \eta(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} \quad (4.12)$$

Unlike the global quantities, $\eta(\vec{r})$ is not the simple reciprocal of $s(\vec{r})$. Their inverse relationship is reflected in the following equation as

$$2 \int s(\vec{r}) \eta(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} = 1 \quad (4.13)$$

The definition of $\eta(\vec{r})$ given in equation (4.11) is not unique and there may be other valid (legitimate) definitions¹⁰⁹ and another choice among the rest would be¹³²

$$2\eta(\vec{r}) = \int -\frac{\delta^2 F(\rho)}{\delta \rho(\vec{r}) \delta \rho(\vec{r}')} - f(\vec{r}') d\vec{r}' \quad (4.14)$$

where the explicit calculation¹⁰⁹ of the integral on the right-hand-side results in η . Although the reciprocity relationship has been lost going from global quantities to their local counterparts a perfect inverse relationship can be retrieved in case of the corresponding kernels^{131,133} as

$$2 \int s(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') \eta(\vec{r}', \vec{r}'') d\vec{r}' = \delta(\vec{r}'' - \vec{r}) \quad (4.15)$$

where the hardness and softness kernels are given by¹³³

$$-2\eta(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') \equiv \frac{\delta u(\vec{r})}{\delta \rho(\vec{r}')} = \frac{\delta u(\vec{r}')}{\delta \rho(\vec{r})} = -\frac{\delta^2 F}{\delta \rho(\vec{r}) \delta \rho(\vec{r}')} \quad (4.16a)$$

and

$$-s(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') \equiv \frac{\delta \rho(\vec{r}')}{\delta u(\vec{r})} = \frac{\delta \rho(\vec{r})}{\delta u(\vec{r}')} \quad (4.16b)$$

where $u(\vec{r})$ is a modified potential defined as

$$u(\vec{r}) = v(\vec{r}) - \mu \quad (4.16c)$$

It can be shown¹³³ easily that these kernels are related to the corresponding local quantities as

$$\eta(\vec{r}) \equiv \frac{1}{N} \int \eta(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') \rho(\vec{r}') d\vec{r}' \quad (4.17a)$$

and

$$s(\vec{r}) \equiv \int s(\vec{r}, \vec{r}') d\vec{r}' \quad (4.17b)$$

It may be noted that the two variable linear response functions can be generated by calculating the change in electron density at a point by varying the external potential somewhere else as

$$\left[\frac{\delta \rho(\vec{r})}{\delta v(\vec{r}')} \right]_N = \frac{\delta^2 E}{\delta v(\vec{r}) \delta v(\vec{r}')} = \left[\frac{\delta \rho(\vec{r}')}{\delta v(\vec{r})} \right]_N \quad (4.18)$$

These local quantities have been shown⁹³ to be important in understanding the theory of metals through their following identification with the local density of states at the Fermi level, $g(\epsilon_F, \vec{r})$ and the total density of states at the Fermi level, $g(\epsilon_F)$ both measured at 0 K,

$$s(\vec{r}) = g(\epsilon_F, \vec{r}) \quad (4.19a)$$

$$g = g(\epsilon_F) \quad (4.19b)$$

$$\text{and } f(\vec{r}) = \frac{g(\epsilon_F, \vec{r})}{g(\epsilon_F)} \quad (4.19c)$$

Equation (4.19) in connection with equation (4.09) provides⁹³ additional insights into the electronic theory of chemisorption and catalysis in terms of low-energy density fluctuations¹³⁴.

It has been understood³⁸ that the refined versions of equation (2.14), the key equations in explaining HSAB principle, would involve the local quantities and incorporating external potential effects we have³⁸

$$\nabla N = \frac{\nabla \mu^0 + \int f_a(\vec{r}) \nabla v_a(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} - \int f_p(\vec{r}) \nabla v_p(\vec{r}) d\vec{r}}{2(\eta_p + \eta_a)}$$

and

$$\nabla E = -\frac{[\nabla \mu^0 + \int f_a(\vec{r}) \nabla v_a(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} - \int f_p(\vec{r}) \nabla v_p(\vec{r}) d\vec{r}]^2}{4(\eta_p + \eta_a)} \quad (4.20)$$

Berkowitz¹³⁵ tried to understand the fate of 'frontier controlled' reactions associated with a small change along the reaction coordinate and obtained the following Clapeyron type equation,

$$\nabla N = \frac{\int f_a(\vec{r}) \nabla v_a(\vec{r}) d\vec{r} - \int f_p(\vec{r}) \nabla v_p(\vec{r}) d\vec{r}}{2(\eta_p + \eta_a)} \quad (4.21)$$

Therefore, the induced electron flow would increase with increasing both the frontier quantity ($f_a - f_b$) and the Fukui function overlap and/or by decreasing the hardness sum, i.e. a typical s-s interaction, 'Frontier-controlled' reactions have also been understood in terms of local softness variations¹⁰⁹ as well as by using the 'apparatus' density functional theory¹³⁶.

Concluding remarks

Density functional theory of two important concepts in chemistry, viz. the chemical potential which measures the propensity of charge transfer from or to a chemical species and the chemical hardness (both global and local), a measure of likelihood of that charge transfer process, has been reviewed. HSAB principle and frontier orbital theory of chemical reactivity are now understood better. A more general theory of chemical reactivity encompassing a variety of chemical reactions is still lacking. It may be necessary to bring in the higher order derivatives in the analysis. Local hardness suffers from the drawback of ambiguity in its definition. Some more conditions are needed to resolve this problem. Local softness, however, does not face this trouble. Among all the quantities discussed, the local softness seems to contain maximum information. In order to gain insights into the chemical reactivity, chemisorption and catalysis local softness is expected to be the most important index. In particular, different fluctuation formulas for local softness should be explored in great detail. Connection of density functional theory with semiempirical electronic structure theories (zero differential overlap type) deserves a closer scrutiny. Finally, it is hoped¹³⁷ that a complete theory for diverse chemical problems in terms of chemical potential and chemical hardness would be obtained in future within the density functional theory.

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CHATTARAJ : ELECTRONEGATIVITY AND HARDNESS : A DENSITY FUNCTIONAL TREATMENT

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